

THE NEED FOR IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING FOLKLORE

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the need for improving the methodology of teaching folk science in the form, introduced at all stages of Education and various innovative methods of teaching as well.

At present, with the beginning of wide efforts to bring distance learning processes to a new level of quality there is a requirement of the period of proper design of folklore lessons among other disciplines. In the process, there is a need to conduct scientific research on the teaching of the laws of development on the basis of the characteristics of oral and written creativity, the system and composition of genres, the influence of each other on the activity of students. Because in the system of continuing education, special attention is paid to the study and teaching of oral and written literature differently. Therefore, the formation of knowledge, skills, skills of students in the field of features of oral and written literature in harmony and continuity, interrelationship, consistent development in folklore lessons is one of the priority tasks.

Subjects related to folklore, as a rule, are taught before the teaching of classical literature as a starting point of the word art in the composition of literature lessons. In this process the attention is given to the work of readers on genres related to folklore, their genesis, the historical roots of origin, the subject area, the composition of images, the composition structure and the poetic language. It is necessary to optimize the consistency and continuity in the content and forms of the work process, and the perfect systematization of didactic exercises.

Although there are fewer didactic materials about folklore that are given in the textbooks, it can be said that the content is at the level of today's requirements for innovation. Such materials are suitable from elementary and upper-class textbooks on high school and college textbooks. In particular, in philology, preschool and primary education students are specially allocated hours of folklore classes. As a result, it is necessary to accurately determine the methods of teaching them both online and offline. There is no doubt that the materials on

the oral creativity of the people in the textbook in the teaching of folklore not only encourage memorization, but also exercises for the development of skills of speech cultivation, logical thinking and practical influence on the development of scientific thinking of students.

It is very important that teachers in the field of folklore prepare specially for the lessons of professional compatibility and folklore. Only then it is possible to raise the level of teaching of folklore to the level that meets the requirements of the educational standard.

The development and implementation of forms and methods of teaching folklore in the education of learners with high moral qualities, effective organization of educational work in accordance with modern requirements requires the improvement of methods of teaching folklore in innovative ways in the distance learning environment.

Since it is envisaged to teach folklore at all stages of continuous education such as primary, general secondary, secondary special and higher education, it is necessary to determine the methods by which students gradually develop their knowledge about it. In particular, the text of folklore dictates the widespread use of such methods as analysis-synthesis, comparison, identification, generalization and conclusion of mental activity. Each word or sentence in it attracts special attention. Even a small proverb requires an analysis in the harmony of language and thought. For example, the proverb (meaning: Like father, like son), in cooperation with readers, can be analyzed using different methods.

1. From the point of view of folklore. It is revealed that this small text is the product of the oral creativity of the people, its belonging to the genre of "proverb", the anonymity by whom it was created, the migration from the mouth to the mouth (traditions) of living.

2. From the point of view of linguistics. In this case, it is determined that the proverb is derived from oral speech, the composition of the phrase expressed by it is a syntactic phrase from such parts of speech as the determinant of the genitive case, position, possessive, verb, morphologically the proverb consists of 2 nouns, 1 adverb, 1 verb, phonetically the first 2 words consist of 3 syllables, on this basis a whole picture of the construction of words in the proverb, word combinations is formed. the sentence in which they are written with their participation.

3. From the point of view of literary studies. Since the words in the proverb have a portable meaning in addition to their own meaning, it is based on the fact that the image of "olma" appears in it, in the first case it is used in the image of parents, in the second case it is used in the image of a child.

At the next stage, it is possible to organize a similar analysis of another proverb as a creative task. Such analysis plays an important role in ensuring science coherence and cohesion.

Before the organization of folk lessons, it will be necessary to study the purpose, functions, printouts and components of the state educational standard in this regard, the base educational plans for each stage of education, the size of the teaching load allocated to the teaching of the oral creativity of the people in them, their distribution by classes, courses, conduct lessons on the content.

In the process of designing folk lessons, the implementation of their object activities on the basis of the technology of student activation is determined by:

- mastering the material of folklore and creating knowledge about it;
- generalization of the acquired knowledge on the basis of comparison;

- draw conclusions on the basis of generalized knowledge;
- intended use in educational activities of assignments on small or large-scale, prose, poetic, poetic-prose, folk material of dramatic type aimed in developing of thought;
 - being able to apply the theoretical knowledge generated by folklore material to different situations (word, word combination required from within the text, finding the image, identifying the folk figurative expressions given in the text, finding similarities, classification);
 - ability to apply the acquired knowledge, skills and skills in practice, etc.

In order to transform the student into an active subject of the distance learning process, to ensure his participation in education with interest, among other subjects, it is necessary to establish a practical direction of folklore education, to involve interactive methods in the process of teaching and learning, to bring the teaching assignments into a non-standard test form, to recommend the artistic sources. Through this, the interactivity of the readers is developed. For example, in the process of working on puzzles from the "find a partner" method, students can use the following in teaching the nature of the genre of the riddle, its poetic features. Because the condition of the method is focused on the listener, just like the purpose and function of the riddle genre, it attracts attention by motivating him to "find". In this process learners are trained in attention, resourcefulness and language sensitivity. This method can serve to ensure the cooperation of the student and the teacher in distance education.

Sometimes during such an electronic exercise, it is also possible to record the beginning part of the selected text and hand over the remaining part to the reader to continue. Then the given task is controlled electronically and the reader receives a response. It will be more effective if the task from this is based on speed.

Attitude is expressed by sending stickers of different positive and negative meaning to those who have and have not eaten the condition.

Folklore education requires that cognitive scientists know, think, understand what they have heard or read about existence, Society, event, historical reality, artistic tissue, imaginary and life fiction, lyrical interpretation, and be able to correctly, understandably, logically express their thoughts, views on these. For this purpose, it is considered necessary to formulate in the students the skills of being able to use units related to folklore.

On the basis of the program of folklore education, it is necessary to correctly select the educational material and its dependence on the system of teaching assignments, therefore, in the textbooks on science, it is necessary to improve the selection and consistency of the topics related to it due to the practical importance of education, to update the texts of exercises, to determine the

It was observed that folklore materials included in the textbooks were selected based on the following criteria:

- materials were chosen from simple to complex, depending on how the volume-structure grew from the appearance of small text to the appearance of a large text (for example, in the 5th grade textbook, a small volume of Proverbs and riddles, in which the content was thoughtful, then in the 6th grade, similar compact folk songs, in the 7th grade, "Essen", in;
- at first it is planned to provide and strengthen the assimilation of knowledge about the ancient (proverb, riddle, legend, narration, fairy tale, song), then the genres that appeared

after it (such as epic, anecdote);

- attention is paid to the fact that the presented material is associated with the life of students, their individual age characteristics, as well as their interest (for example, 5-6-graders are not interested in the fairy tale, while 8-9-graders are not interested in the fairy tale, so fairy tales are included in the textbooks 5-graders);

- the development of the period is also taken into account that it is reflected in folk genres (if, for example, the example of the epic "Alpomish" can be explained to readers about seeds, the mutual unification of seeds, it is possible to mean the absorption of seed relations, on the contrary, on the example of the epic "Ravshan");

- it is taken into account that it is possible to study at the educational stage in a continuous connection with such subjects as history, linguistics, literary studies, geography, etc.

Observations show that even in distance education, elements such as the purpose, method and tools of teaching, organizational forms, control are covered. If there is not enough work on the folk materials given to the teachers in this, it is clear that the shortcomings arise if the content of theoretical knowledge is not determined, although it is Elementary in terms of the genres of folk oral creativity to the students. Therefore, the theory of folklore should be taught to express information in a clear, understandable speech on the issues of The Associated genre, genre, composition, image, lingvopoetics, to receive the information delivered and to analyze them critically, to process it, to summarize it through various points of view, to draw conclusions, to think independently, to sympathize with their own ideas. Such a pedagogical approach plays an important role in the cultivation of pupils' activity.

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